
Research Paper

Sexism in Modern Day Sports; Using World Cup Kiss Crisis as Case Study

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Abstract

This study examines sexism, gender inequality, and power abuse in women's football by analysing the 2023 "World Cup Kiss Crisis" incident that happened between former Spanish Football Federation President, Luis Rubiales and Spain's Women's team all-time top scorer, Jenni Hermoso. Since another FIFA Women's World Cup is around the corner, The study delved deeper into this past incident to examine how systemic sexism and patriarchal leadership structures continue to influence women's experiences in modern sports, both on and off the field. The study uses discourse analysis to explore how language, media framing, and institutional reactions influenced public comprehension of the incident. Only secondary data from news reports, journal papers, social media posts, and official government statements were used for this research work. The findings suggest that the non-consensual kiss was not only an isolated instance of wrongdoing, but also a reflection of larger gendered power disparities in sports institutions. It focused on Media framing, social media activity, and collective action by players and supporters who demanded for accountability. The paper also ties the episode to the ideas behind Title IX and Title VII which is in connection to workplace harassment and discrimination legislation, despite the fact that these laws do not apply directly in Spain. Ultimately, the crisis revealed fundamental flaws in sports governance and highlighted the significance of ethical leadership, transparency, and gender equity. According to the findings, public pressure and organized resistance can act as catalysts for institutional transformation and increased protection of women in sports.

Keywords: Sexism, Gender Inequality, Power Abuse, Crisis Management, Media Framing

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Luis Rubiales Kisses Jenni Hermoso Without Her Consent.

Image by: Catalan News

Introduction

Sexism is the stereotype one suffers based on their sex. This research has re-defined it as the unequal treatment and discrimination that female athletes suffer because of their gender. This inequity has manifested in variety of ways, including poorer income, fewer chances, and less media attention as compared to their male counterparts. Despite the fact that women's sports frequently display amazing talent and athleticism, they receive less attention, support, and money. This disparity stems from long-held cultural biases that have historically underestimated women's ability in sports and other areas of life.

For instance, soccer as a sport is generally quiet a bias sport that has over the years come under criticism for promoting male dominance, gender biases and sexism. There is a vast difference between the bonuses women receive at big events like the World Cup as compared to what the men earn. The 2023 World Cup held in Australia and New Zealand from July 20th to August 20th saw a rise in the Women's final prize money to about \$110 Million which is still four times lower than the \$440 Million received by the men's World Cup winning team, which was the amount presented to Argentina for emerging as winners at the 2022 World Cup held in Qatar (Forbes, 2023).

Sexism has become one of the terrible things that has lingered for years in football. Most football offices across the world including the International Federation of Association Football's (FIFA) headquarters in Zurich, has more male staffs than women. The few women employees in the sports industry are usually treated as though they are being done a favour. A typical example is the Luis Rubiales and Jenni's incident which came to confirm the injustices happening to women in the industry. During the 2023 Women's World Cup finals' medal presentation, Jenni Hermoso

was kissed on the lips by the Spanish Football Federation (RFEF) President, Luis Rubiales, a kiss she later described as unconsented.

After winning a big tournament like the world cup for the first time, it is only normal to see people celebrating in different ways. Everyone due to the adrenaline, are likely to express their emotions in unique ways, either by an extreme joy and celebration for the winning team or an intense disappoint and sorrow for the losing side. These emotions are shown by some through the shedding of tears, hugs, screams, just to name but a few. According to the football rules, three things are bound to happen in a match, a win, a loss or a draw, and whichever comes the way of a team, must be accepted in good faith (IFAB, 2023). The results must be accepted, but in cases where a team feels cheated or gets dissatisfied with a result, then the right procedure must be followed to seek redress.

Spain played the World Cup finals against England and took the trophy with just a lone goal. While, the Spanish side were celebrating, the English team on the other hand were heartbroken for losing yet another final. Their popular slogan “It is coming home” was not achieved. Unfortunately, Spain short lived the celebration of a historic moment due to an awkward behaviour from Luis Rubiales. He inappropriately kissed Jenni Hermoso on the lips as she walked to receive her medal. The moment which was captured on camera soon started sparking negative reactions and headlines that over-shadowed Spain’s success story.

The all-time top scorer and Midfielder, Jenni Hermoso in her first interview after walking off the stage, when asked what she made of the kiss said “I didn’t enjoy it” (Los Angeles Times, 2023). After the team arrived home, she was quoted in another interview saying ““It was a completely spontaneous mutual gesture due to the immense joy of winning a World Cup. The

president and I have a great relationship, his behaviour towards all of us has been exemplary, and it was a natural expression of affection and gratitude,” (Diario AS, 2023). Also, Rubiales in his interviews after the incident said “Jenni lifted me from the ground, held me close and after comforting her, I asked her for a piquito, a small kiss, and she said fine” (ABC News, 2023).

Few days later, Jenni Hermoso granted another interview, and this time around, she came out clean with a confession that she was under pressure from the RFEF. She said they threatened her and also gave her words to say to the press concerning the kiss “I have been under continuous pressure to make a statement that could justify Mr. Luis Rubiales’ actions, not only that, but in different ways and through different people, the RFEF has pressured my surroundings (family, friends, teammates, etc.) to give a testimony that had little or nothing to do with my feelings” (Just Women Sports, 2023). She gave this revelation on X (Twitter) and that began the beginning of a whole scandal. Something which was initially perceived as a minor incident, because it was not handled properly, rapidly intensified and went out of proportion to become a full-blown crisis situation.

Rational

This research work was to find the extent to which sexual abuse, sexism biases, and masculinity is still rampant in our modern-day sports and the level of damage this is still causing. It probed deeper to find the root causes, how it is affecting the women playing the game as well as those occupying administrative roles. After the findings, it came up with some suggestions which will help make modern sports equal and free for all. The Rubiales-Jenni situation followed an interesting trend and captured some ugly moments where the behaviour of Luis Rubiales and the RFEF were questioned by many people. The curiosity of embanking on this research work

however, was also to know what other hidden misconducts were possibly happening behind the scenes before Jenni's situation escalated? For instance, the dismissal of the Head coach who led the team to lifting their first World Cup trophy. He was sacked after a video of him inappropriately touching a female staff member surfaced.

In addition, why would over 80 players rally behind Hermoso to call for the dissolving of the administration, especially the technical members of the team? Why did football fans in other countries join in the fight to consistently protest until they saw that actions were taken by the necessary international soccer bodies against Rubiales for him to step down? (CNN, 2023). Another area this research work delved into was the reactions that came from the RFEF as a federation. Many wondered if they were a Federation for all or for Luis Rubiales? As a Federation, the core mandate should be to serve the interest of everyone playing football in Spain, as well as the administrators.

The variables present in this research work which includes both dependent and independent are the probes into the nexus of gender, power and sports utilizing the "World Cup Kiss Crisis" to highlight systemic sexism. The Rubiales-Hermoso affair is seen not only as an example of personal misbehaviour but also as a metaphor for the larger challenges that women face in football. It demonstrates how patriarchal control in athletic bodies leads to the marginalization and objectification of female athletes, emphasizing the critical need for structural reforms.

This study is intimately related to conversations about how unequal power relations exist on the pitch and in boardrooms, which enable gender-based abuse. Also, the article discusses how public and institutional reactions to gender-based crises can affect change. Hermoso's subsequent reaction, backed by players and fans, sparked global discussions about sexism in sports, prompting

the RFEF and FIFA to take action. This highlights the ability of social activism and collective action to change long-standing discriminatory norms. In terms of this research, the notion that crises, when properly leveraged, can serve as watershed moments for greater gender parity in sports was confirmed.

Also, the literature review's argument of this work focused on crisis management lapses, Title IX and VII-related comparisons, highlighting how the issue extended beyond athletics and ties to broader legal and ethical concerns. The Hermoso's case is similar to scenarios of educational and professional harassment, implying that elite sports suffer from the same structural failings as other industries. This essay establishes a solid platform for future research into how women in sports continue to resist and modify the structures that oppress them by drawing the dots between organizational neglect, individual trauma, and cultural misogyny.

Research Questions:

RQ1: How does Sexism, bias and gender inequality promote abuse of women in Soccer?

RQ2: How did Striker, Jenni Hermoso's battle and victory against the former RFEF President, Luis Rubiales and the RFEF, help address inequalities and disrespect in women's soccer in Spain?

Literature Review

The FIFA Women's World Cup, which began in 1991 in China and was first won by the United States, has grown into becoming one of the most important global stage competitions for the women. Although it continues to face deep disparities in pay, media coverage, and institutional support compared to men's football. The competition was built on a prior unofficial women's world

cup in 1970 and 1971 respectively, before FIFA formally recognized the women's game. While teams like the United States and Germany have dominated the competition, the broader academic issue centres on how women's football has fought for legitimacy inside male-dominated football systems. This research work focused on the Rubiales-Hermoso controversy which took place in Sydney Australia, during the 2023 FIFA Women's World Cup finals between Spain and England, to assess how abuse, inequality and sexism still has a room in our modern-day sports. It provided a critical foundation for understanding how gender, authority, and media discourse influence.

One of the definitions given to crisis is that, it is the unpreparedness for a threat that hits an organization or an individual, and negatively impact their reputation (Benoit, 2015; Ulmer et al., 2019). *The World Cup kiss situation was classified by some articles as being a Title IX and Sexual Harassment case. The Los Angeles Times in their online article posted on August, 28 stated that, Rubiales being the Federation's President at the time should have known that he was Jenni's boss since the player worked directly under his authority, thereby making an uninvited kiss a clear issue of sexual harassment (2023).*

The observations made so far regarding issues of Title IX, indicates that the defensive approach of crisis control mechanism is what most people resort to anytime they are faced with scandals, followed by an apology be it genuine or not. Others only apologize when the issue gets out of control. Example of a similar situation is the University of North Alabama's sexual assault case which involved a student named Jane Doe and a visiting Professor who was on one year contract with the school, David B. Dickerson. The assault which took place when they were on an off-campus trip to Orlando for the International Collegiate Sales Competition, was reported by

Jane when they returned to campus but the school's authority reluctantly failed to take any positive steps until they saw the story in the news (Drumheller & Kinsky, 2021).

The RFEF took the media and the paparazzi who were present at the finals of the competition for granted until the following day when they started seeing different headlines, framing the kiss in diverse dimensions. Instead of the press focusing on the team's success, they decided to feed on the kiss incident. There are five types of framing mechanisms which are usually used by the media to publish stories. These includes, Attribution of responsibility, Economic frame, Morality frame, Human-Interest frame and Conflict Frame (An & Gower, 2009). Following the trends of this case, the very common frames used by most media across the globe was the Conflict, Attribution of Responsibility, Human-Interest, and the Morality Frames. Conflict "is used to explain the disagreement among individuals, groups and organizations (Neuman et al., 1992).

The morality frame examines the situation through the lenses of religion, social standards and morals (Neuman et al., 1992). Human Interest "brings a human or an emotional angle to the presentation or an event, issue or problem", and the Attribution of responsibility frame is when a situation is shared or blamed on an individual or a group of people (Semetko & Valkenburg, 2000). News Media play a very important role in shaping the minds and opinions of people by directing them to consume and believe what the press is feeding them with. All too soon, winning the World Cup which was the biggest achievement for the Spain was forgotten as most media outlets re-focused people's attention on the kiss incident, even those who reported a bit on the World Cup achievement combined it with the kiss crisis.

The criticisms started pouring in for Rubiales who was exposed by Jenni for lies, manipulations and abuse. He made matters worse by arrogantly responding to the critics as "idiots"

instead of simply rendering a sincere apology, and also refused to resign from his position, "I've come under a lot of pressure. Perhaps somebody will like to remove me on Monday. But we live in a country of laws. Is a consensual kiss enough to remove me? I'm going to fight until the end. I hope the law is followed, and that there's no reason to remove me, it won't happen!" (ESPN, 2023). He should have just apologized when feminist groups, football enthusiasts and women across the globe started criticizing his actions on X (Twitter), they called him a sexist and called for his dismissal either by the Spanish Federation or FIFA.

Meanwhile, Sexism is also seen as the negative attitude and discrimination towards someone based on their sex, either at their workplace or any environment they find themselves. In most cases, the perpetrators are men (Expositor, et al., 1998). There are two types of sexism as stated by Cameron, the Traditional and the New shape. Traditional sexism is "an attitude of prejudice or discriminatory behaviour based on the supposed inferiority or differences of women as a group" (1977). The new shape works in a disguise form where people pretend sexism does not exist until it shows its ugly head. Sexual assaults cases are also usually defended and denied if the perpetrators are men, they impose their masculinity in defence of the crime against their victims. It then becomes the victim's words against them (Edwards & Dardis, 2022).

Gender inequality issues are predominantly affecting the smooth running of sports around the globe, thereby making women less represented in Sports leadership positions. The factors promoting the gender inequality in the sporting world includes "Patriarchal selection practices and organizational cultures reinforcing this inequity, despite the evidence that men in leadership roles recognize the problem. While gender equity policies exist, actions to pursue gender equity are more limited. Patriarchal language, gendered stereotypes and person-profiling still persist,

resulting in specific emotional and practical challenges for women in sports leadership positions, which is as a result of patriarchal and cultural practices (Evans & Pfister, 2021).

This imbalance structure hinders balanced decision making, especially the ones related to the progress of women soccer and its administration, promotes violence against women in sports, and also other assaults and harassments. This was what Rubiales and the Spanish federation did to Jenni and shamelessly threatened and forced her to lie to cover them up. Her U-turn on the matter did not just clear her conscience but also brought liberation for other football players around the world who may have dealt or are dealing with abuses.

Viewing Jenni's Incident Through the Lenses of Title IX and VII

This research work has delved deeper into the titles IX and VII laws to see how the incident that occurred between Jenni Hermoso and Luis Rubiales falls under the violations of any of these laws.

Title IX

Title IX is a 1972 law passed in the United States. It is part of a larger set of education regulations that prohibits gender-based discrimination in school access and programs. This law applies to all schools, colleges, and universities that receive federal funds. While Title IX covers a wide range of topics, it is best known for ensuring that women and girls have equal opportunities in sports. Before Title IX, many schools did not provide girls' sports teams equal rights, or if they did, they were underfunded. The legislation played a role in the transformation of this situation. Schools must now give equal opportunities to both boys and girls in sports and in other school

activities. Title IX also protects students from sexual harassment and assault in schools, emphasizing the need for schools to take action to prohibit such behaviour.

In recent years, Title IX has been utilized to advocate for improved treatment for women in all fields of education and athletics. It argues that women deserve respect, safety, and equitable treatment not just on paper, but in real life. Schools may face legal consequences if they disregard reports of harassment or allow a hazardous atmosphere to persist. Rubiales kissing Hermoso without her permission was described by many as a textbook case of misogyny and power abuse in sports. While Title IX does not work in Spain, the principles it represents, such as defending women's rights, combating harassment, and demanding responsibility, are part of a global movement. The episode demonstrated why rules such as Title IX are still important to ensure that athletes, particularly women, are treated with dignity and respect.

Title VII

Unlike some parts of the world where laws do not properly function, the Title VII of the Civil Rights Act of 1964 is a key federal statute in the United States and is very active and forbids employment discrimination based on race, colour, religion, gender, or national origin. It was an important component of the larger Civil Rights Movement, which sought to provide equal treatment and opportunities for all individuals in all parts of society, including the workplace. The law applies to all employers with 15 or more employees, including federal, state, and local governments, as well as employment agencies and labour organizations.

This law is critical for safeguarding workers against unfair treatment during hiring, firing, promotions, wages, job training, and other employment terms and conditions. For example, a company cannot refuse to hire someone based only on their ethnicity or reject a promotion based

on their gender. Title VII also makes it illegal for employers to retaliate against employees who file discrimination complaints or participate in an inquiry or litigation under the Act. The protection against sexual harassment in the workplace is an important part of Title VII. This includes unwanted sexual advances, solicitations for sexual favours, and other sexually-motivated verbal or physical harassments. The legislation also prohibits harassment based on a person's sex, even if it is not sexual, such as making derogatory statements about women or men in general. Employers must prevent and handle such harassment in order to maintain a safe and respected workplace environment.

In addition, religious accommodations are another key aspect of Title VII which encourages employers to reasonably accommodate an employee's religious beliefs or practices unless doing so would cause undue hardship on the business. This can include flexible scheduling for religious holidays or allowing certain types of dress. The goal is to allow employees to observe their religion without facing penalties or discrimination at work. It is an effective law that promotes workplace fairness and equality. It fosters a more inclusive and respectful workplace by outlawing discrimination and requires employers to accept diversity. The Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (EEOC) enforces Title VII and investigates complaints, which helps to protect workers' rights and hold employers accountable when they violate the law.

Methodology

This study applied a discourse analysis to investigate how language, power, and institutional authority affected public perceptions of the Rubiales-Hermoso controversy. Rather than focusing solely on what occurred, the research investigated how major individuals used

words, declarations, and how media platforms were used to create alternative interpretations of reality. The scandal became a hotbed of debate over meaning, culpability, and validity, thanks to government pronouncements, social media posts, and reactions from FIFA and the audience.

Data for this research work was derived from secondary sources such as journal papers, news reports, social media posts, and YouTube videos. These materials establish a public discursive space for framing and debating the event. Tweets, hashtags, and online comments were particularly the most valuable tool since they revealed how ordinary people viewed and responded to the incident. These digital connections allowed dominant narratives to be challenged and alternative perspectives to be heard.

Jenni Hermoso's X comment had a significant impact on the discourse. She utilized terminology to portray the kiss as an abuse of power rather than a misunderstanding, labelling herself as "vulnerable" and a "victim" of a non-consensual act. This choice of language upended the celebratory football narrative and reframed the episode as an instance of gendered misconduct. Her remark served as a counter-discourse, requiring public and institutional accountability.

The RFEF's answer exemplifies how dominant institutions utilize rhetoric to maintain authority. The federation attempted to damage Hermoso's credibility by accusing her of lying and threatened legal action. This statement aimed to divert attention away from their shameful conduct and re-direct it toward the victim's integrity. Such tactics are typical in power battles, as institutions employ legal and moral rhetoric to silence opponents and retain supremacy.

FUTPRO, defended Hermoso and questioned the federation's framing. By denouncing behaviour that infringed women's "dignity," the union framed the problem within a larger context of gender rights and workplace protection. This phrase validated Hermoso's experience and reframed her as a worker whose rights had been violated, rather than an individual at odds with authority. FUTPRO's engagement established a new institutional voice that challenged the RFEF's narrative.

Overall, the scandal evolved into a debate over different conceptions of power, gender, and responsibility. Hermoso and FUTPRO utilized language to reveal inequity and demanded justice, but the RFEF employed legal and moral rhetoric to justify its leadership. This conflict was exacerbated by social media, which enabled multiple voices to circulate and compete. This discourse demonstrated, how language is not only a means of narrating events, but also a significant tool for negotiating social and institutional authority.

On August 25th, Jenni Hermoso made an official announcement on the social media handle X that she felt “vulnerable and a victim of an impulse-driven, sexist who kissed her without any consent from her part”. This statement pushed the RFEF who suddenly forgot their role as a bigger umbrella whose core duty was to protect the players. They released a first statement to condemn the victim, calling her a liar “we must state that Mrs. Jennifer Hermoso lies in every statement she makes against the President” (Washington Post, 2023). A part of the second statement released by the RFEF which they later deleted, threatened legal actions against the victim on behalf of Luis, “The RFEF and the president giving the content of the press release from Futpro Union, will initiate the corresponding legal actions”.

The union that represents women's players in Spain before the release of the official statements by the Spanish Federation, rallied behind Jenni, "my union FUTPRO, in coordination with my agency TMJ are taking care of defending my interests and are being the interlocutors on this matter". The statement from FUTPRO reads "we express our firm and resounding condemnation of conducts that violet the dignity of women" (Diario AS, 2023).

Stakeholders Actions and Responses

In the midst of all the social media banter, FIFA, the world governing body for Football, Beach Soccer and Futsal, launched an investigation into the matter. While the investigations were ongoing, Luis Rubiales was given a provisional 90 days ban. Within the same period there was protest and live demonstrations going on in Spain, in front of the office of the RFEF, just so that Rubiales would resign but he refused to vacate his post both in Spain and at the Union of European Football (UEFA) where he served as Vice President. On October 30, FIFA released another official statement banning Rubiales from all football related activities for 3 years. The Disciplinary Committee explained that he was found guilty of breaching article 13 of the FIFA Disciplinary code, which is concerning "Offensive behaviour and violations of principles of fair play". (FIFA, 2023).

Prior to FIFA's final verdict, Spain's President also stepped into the situation to start proceedings to suspend Luis Rubiales since he would not willingly resign, but the rules of FIFA prohibit external or political figures from meddling in football matters. Hence, the only way for the president, was to file for a legal proceeding which helped to suspend Luis. At this point, he was still speaking at press interviews asking if they think the issue was so serious for him to resign? "Do you think this incident is so serious that I should go, after the best management in the history

of Spanish football? Let me tell you: I'm not going to resign. I'm not going to resign. I'm not going to resign!" (ESPN, 2023).

Striker Jenni Hermoso

Analysis

The analysis was done focusing on posts made on some social media platforms from the time the crisis began on August 20, till middle of November 2023. The specific social media platforms used were, X, YouTube and Facebook.

More than 120 messages were posted on the Social Media handle X during the “kiss crisis”, and here are just some few messages that stood out and used for this research purpose. The main hashtag was #Metoo, then most of the other news media channels used #LuisRubialeskiss scandal, and #Kiss scandal.

(Reuters, August 25,2023).

“Live Protesters call for Football Federation President, Luis Rubiales over kiss scandal”

(The New York Times, September 5, 2023).

“Breaking News: Jorge Vilda, the coach of the Spanish national soccer team that won the Women’s World Cup last month, was ousted on Tuesday by the country’s soccer federation. His boss, Luis Rubiales is embroiled in scandal over a non-consensual kiss.”

(Dr Rachel B., August 26, 2023).

“Staggering Scenes: Governing body says it will take ‘necessary action’ against female players protesting over Luis Rubiales kiss scandal & threatened to sue the 79 players who signed the letter in which they refused to play as long Rubiales remained.”

(LBC, August 26, 2023).

“11 members of Spain’s coaching team quit over Luis Rubiales kiss scandal”

(Philip L., September 10, 2023).

“Suspended Spanish soccer federation President, Luis Rubiales says he will not resign after kiss scandal.

(BBC News, November 6, 2023).

“Spain forward Jenni Hermoso said she received threats amid Luis Rubiales kiss scandal”
Catalan News, September 10th, 2023).

“Breaking: Rubiales quits as head of Spanish Football Federation over Hermoso kiss scandal.

Luis Rubiales also steps down as UEFA Vice President after kissing player during World Cup final”

(TuckFrum, September 11, 2023).

Disgraced Head of Spanish Soccer Luis Rubiales Finally Resigns after World Cup kiss scandal,

There was only one contradictory tweet found which was posted by a verified handle called TopMG, where he claimed his quote was from an interview granted by former FC Barcelona Forward, Mephis Depay. This was posted on the 26th August, 2023 saying “I didn’t speak about this but after yesterday’s speech I couldn’t hold back, I talk to my bro. Rubes, on Zoom and I can confirm, there ain’t no devil in his eyes. I would let him kiss my girl if I had to, and I hope FIFA takes my word and stops their investigations at once”

There were other interesting headlines to the story on YouTube from channels of all the big media firms across the globe and other individually owned YouTube channels, about 70 different videos were posted concerning the story between the space of four months, that is from

the 20th of August to November 11. Example of some of these are, ABC News, Good Morning America, Reuters, Sky New, BBC, CNN, RFEF Official YouTube handle and many more.

The Guardian's headline for their YouTube channel the day after the incident was "Luis Rubiales kisses Jenni Hermoso after Spain wins World Cup" (2023, Rubiales kisses Jenni, 0:00-1:38).

3 months after the incident, CNN posted "Spanish Soccer chief apologies for giving unwanted kiss" (CNN,2023; Rubiales apology, 0:00- 5:42).

"Spanish football chief expected to quit over World Cup Kiss scandal" (France 24, 2023).

"FIFA Suspends Rubiales but Spain Football Federation Accuses player of Lying About Kiss at World Cup" (CRUZ, 2023; kiss scandal, 0:00-6:13).

The Facebook posts were not much, they were just a little over 20, and were mainly from the news channels and websites' official handles. I did not see individual posts, and concluded maybe it is because they did not use the above listed hashtags. Other handles like, Instagram, Ticktock, Snapchat and the rest were not considered by this research work.

Discussion

Acknowledging the strong influence of social media and staying alert on the kind of posts to make is one of the best ways to protect one's image. Unlike those days when Journalism use to be stories decided by gatekeepers, this social media era is different, and underrating its power could lead to serious consequences. Social media is also called "New Media and plays significant roles in our daily interactions, Examples of such are, Facebook, Snapchat, WhatsApp, Messenger, X, Facetime, YouTube, LinkedIn, E-mails, Instagram, Tiktok, Find Friends, just to name but few. These various platforms act as official platforms for disseminating news and interacting with one

another. They are used for Public Relation works like promoting brands, for media relations purposes, event planning, reputation management and most importantly they can easily blow-up crisis if not managed properly. In our modern society where everyone seems to spend most of their time at work trying to make more money, one of the easiest ways of staying up to date with what is going on around the world is through social media (Jeremy H., 2018).

There has been some serious crisis that had the news break first on social media before other major traditional media houses could carry the stories. One of such examples was the Earthquake that happened in Turkey and in some parts of Syria in 2023 which took so many lives. Some people who were at the area where the incident took place, although were in danger still found a way to record and do Facebook live even in the midst of the tragedy. A very touching video came from a 17-year-old boy, Taha Erdem, who sent a goodbye message to his father from the rubbles. In the video, he mentioned that he was really thirsty and as part of his last desires wished to get the opportunity to drink water. He then concluded the video with tears and words of goodbye saying in case his dad didn't hear from him again, then it is either his battery was dead or maybe he did not survive the wait.

Fortunately, he was traced and rescued by the rescue team after surviving for more than 10 days in the rubbles (Daily Mail, 2023). At the beginning of this crisis, the Turkish President, Recep Tayyip Erdogan in a state emergency address, said they were fine, and would need some first aid kits and medicines but later, the things that were posted on social media said otherwise concerning the magnitude of damage the earthquake had caused. This prompted an immediate action from the Western countries and all other countries all over the world, who stepped in to help the situation with more than just first aid items. (Politico.eu, 2023).

This tragedy also took the life of one of Ghana's talented national soccer players, Christian Atsu who was on loan from England (BBC News, 2023). It was by the help of social media again for his friends and family to locate his body.

In spite of quick dissemination and the proximity of social media news and stories, they also come with some disadvantages like trash-talking, posting of false information and many more. Why this article is laying so much emphasis on social media and the role they play is because Luis Rubiales and the RFEF simply underrated the power of social media and ended up paying for it dearly. He showed pure arrogance and masculinity instead of apologizing and also shamelessly had the backings of the RFEF. The Federation in their official posts made a fool out of themselves by posting edited photos from the incident which showed Rubiales giving Jenni a peg on the chin instead of the kiss on the lips, forgetting that the original picture was all over on social media.

Secondly, they also threatened legal actions against the victim. This made the people and protestors angrier. The sad thing is that, the RFEF forgot that the kiss moment was also captured on videos as well. Few weeks later when they realized their PR staunch wouldn't work, they now resorted to an apology. They posted a video of Luis saying "I have to apologize", Luis Rubiales, said in a video broadcast by the federation, "probably I made a mistake, I have regrets and have to admit it, but it was without bad faith" (The New York Times, 2023).

Many said that his apology was not genuine, and fans criticized him the more saying his body language in the video was not encouraging. This whole situation could have been avoided if they didn't try to use force and to use their positions as leaders to shut Jenni up. Assuming they took the people's posts on X concerning the kiss seriously, and also if Luis had admitted his wrong doing from the start and rendered a sincere apology in the beginning rather than arrogantly trying

to defend his stands and also engaging in blame games and name calling, this whole crisis would have turned out differently (Hearit, 2022).

Conclusion

Despite these challenges, women have made considerable strides in breaking down barriers in sport. The accomplishments of athletes such as Serena Williams, Megan Rapinoe, and Simone Biles, among others, have highlighted the need for greater equality and encouraged reform. Advocacy activities and projects promoting women's sports continue to expand, with the goal of creating a more level playing field in which all athletes, regardless of gender, can prosper and be recognized for their abilities.

Luis Rubiales eventually disgraced himself before stepping down due to the poor manner in which he handled the scandal. He used defence mechanism which in the long run tarnished his reputation and the achievements he took so many years to build. Finding another job in such a reputable position in the future will definitely be a problem for him.

Finally, The RFEF revealed to the world that their competence level was low especially when it comes to handling issues pertaining to women. It is a shame that they exempted Jenni Hermoso from all national team duties after she released a documentary concerning the kiss scandal on Netflix. The federation showed how much they care about power and their personal interest rather than truly serving the people of Spain as well as the playing bodies entrusted in their care.

Limitation

This research did not include or use any primary data. Qualitative interviews with some of the parties involved in this scandal would have helped to make the work more detailed. It totally relied

on other literature work, and the gatherings of information from social media platforms and other websites. There is still more room for future research works on this topic.

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